
EFFECT OF INTAKE DISTORTION ON A TURBOFAN ENGINE

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Abstract:

Extreme maneuvers like take off (high angle of attack) and side slip cause erratic aerodynamic characteristics at the inlet of the engine causing distorted flow at the inlet. These conditions are simulated in a ground test facility with the help of distortion screens to study the engine performance and stability. A base line (non-distorted flow) engine test is done for comparison. The distortion test accounts for the turbomachinery aerodynamic instabilities such as reduced air flow, compressor stall and surge. This leads to a reduction in the engine's performance and stability. Thrust, Turbine Inlet Temperature etc. are calculated to assess the performance of the engine. The surge margin measures the engine stability. The test facility makes use of a circumferential pressure probe arrangement to measure pressure defects at the inlet leading to distortion. The distortion patterns can be classified as circumferential distortion patterns and radial distortion patterns (hub radial patterns and tip radial patterns). They are studied with the help of distortion parameters like intensity and extent. The reduction in the surge margin can be predicted with the help of these distortion parameters using established correlation methods. A comparative study between the baseline and the distortion test is done to assess to effects of distortion.

Key Words: Inlet pressure distortion, Distortion screen, Engine performance, Engine stability, Loss in surge margin.

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 Literature Review

1.1.1 About Distortion

Only during the late 20th century was the effect of distortion on the performance of the engine came to light. It became apparent that these irregularities in the pressure conditions at the inlet of the engine led to imbalance and worse, surging of the compressor. Hence, the study of distortion became vital.

1.1.2 Distortion Phenomenon

Fig 1.1 Typical Airfoil Stall

Distortion occurs mainly due to flow separation. When the flow passes over the airfoil structure at minimum or zero AOA, the pressure is less and the velocity is more till camber, beyond which the pressure increases and velocity decreases. The same flow when it encounters the airfoil at a high AOA (T/O), the flow hits the camber at high velocity and hence flow reversal takes place and results in flow separation.

1.1.3 Need for Distortion Test

Inlet distortion test gives a view on the engine performance during extreme conditions and helps in making the engine fail safe.

Several aircrafts failed, which were not tested for inlet distortion.

E.g. F100 (1954), Hunter (1955), F111 (1966), etc.,

1.2 Types of Distortion

Inlet distortion can be divided into inlet pressure, temperature and flow angle distortion. Inlet pressure distortion (spatial non-uniformity of pressure) is caused due to the shape of the engine intake or high angle of attack maneuver or high cross winds or even side-slip of the aircraft. While, inlet temperature distortion (spatial non-uniformity in temperature) can be caused due to inflow of the hot exhaust gas. Inlet pressure distortion comprises of static and dynamic type, circumferential and radial type or a combination of the two. Each of the type is governed by a distortion parameter like, face average, intensity, extent, etc.

1.3 Methods of Producing Distortion

Distortion produced can be of two types:

1. Time variant
2. Time Invariant

Time Invariant distortion ^[1] can be produced in two methods:

1. Distortion screens
2. Air jet distortion generators

1.4 Test Cell

The given generic turbo-fan engine is tested in two different test cells one being ground mounted and the other roof mounted.

Roof mounting is considered more superior as it takes less time for engine mounting and can also be easily serviced.

1.4.1 Dynamic Engine Control Unit (DECU)

The DECU is responsible for managing the flight performance during all flight conditions. The engine control is achieved in such a way that for a given PLA, a pre-defined NL is maintained by varying the engine parameters. Hence, for any flight condition (with or without distortion) if 100% PLA is given as input to the DECU, 100% NL is achieved as response. The control system directly controls four state variables – fuel flow rate, reheat fuel flow rate, exit nozzle diameter, variable guide vanes, to achieve control over NLc

Fig 1.2 Typical Control System Response

1.4.2 Data Acquisition and Management System (DAMS)

Data acquisition systems serve as the key feature in acquiring millions of data per second. The DAMS incorporated in the test bed links the pressure probes, thermocouples and other measuring devices and the set of computers in the control room. When the run starts, the data from all the instrumentation linked to the engine is recorded for every half of a second. The data from instrumentation are of two types – one for aerodynamic performance and the other for structural health management. Health monitoring data acquisition like strain, vibration, tip clearance etc., are high bandwidth data and are used for online and offline analysis of engine structural health.

Table 1.1 Instrumentation

Sensor Name	Sensor Type	Units	Location
P1avg	Total pressure	psia	Station 1
A1Tavg	Total temperature	deg_C	Station 1
CP2avg	Total pressure	psia	Station 2
T2avg	Total temperature	deg_K	Station 2
CP2DCavg	Total pressure	psia	Station 2d
T2DCavg	Total temperature	deg_K	Station 2d
CP3Cavg	Total pressure	psia	Station 3
T3avg	Total temperature	deg_K	Station 3
PJDCavg	Total pressure	psia	Station 6
TJCavg	Total temperature	deg_C	Station 6
mLPC	Mass flow rate	Kg/sec	Station 1
mHPC	Mass flow rate	Kg/sec	Station 2
XG	Thrust	Kg	-

Wf	Fuel flow rate	gpm	-
NL	Low spool speed	rpm	-
NLc	Corrected low spool speed	%	-
NH	High spool speed	rpm	-
NHc	Corrected high spool speed	%	-
PLA	Pilot Lever Angle	degrees	-
Nozzle_dia	Diameter	inches	Station 8

1.5 Testing

The engine mounted on the test bed is started with the help of air turbine starter which is directly connected to the high-pressure spool through an engine mounted gearbox. Air turbine starter drives the high-pressure spool and, low-pressure spool rotates in turn due to aerodynamic coupling between low pressure and high pressure spools.

The pilot lever directly controls the NLc. As the engine is throttled, NLc increases and hence the mass flow rate of air entering the engine also increases. The DECU is responsible for engine management during flight delivering the optimum engine performance during all conditions. The data from the instrumentation set up at various stations is given as input to the DAMS which processes the data and gives the output in the form of a readable file once the test run is completed.

2. EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

The following procedures are applied to calculate the baseline performance (without the distortion screen) which is then used as a benchmark for calculating the

performance when the engine is subjected to distortion (with the distortion screen). All the performance parameters are corrected to match the sea level static conditions

Table 2.1 List of Corrected Parameters [2]

Parameter	Correction
Corrected Temperature	$\frac{T}{\theta}$
Corrected Pressure	$\frac{P}{\delta}$
Corrected air speed	$\frac{v}{\sqrt{\theta}}$
Corrected air flow rate	$\frac{\dot{m} \cdot \sqrt{\theta}}{\delta}$
Corrected fuel flow rate	$\frac{\dot{w}_f}{\delta \cdot \sqrt{\theta}}$
Corrected Thrust	$\frac{Thrust}{\theta}$
Corrected Power	$\frac{Power}{\delta \cdot \sqrt{\theta}}$

From each test run the data output from DAMS at steady state conditions (constant NLc) is used for calculating the performance parameters.

2.1 Distortion Screen

Distortion screen [1], [3] that matches the desired inlet conditions is selected for the distortion tests. The pressure pattern on the screen is decided by experimental methods.

(Diameter: 'd', Thickness: 0.013d, alpha: 8°, beta: 5°, Inlet Mach Number: 0.3)

Fig 2.1 Location of Distortion Screen (Side View)

Fig 2.2 Distortion Screen (Front View)

2.2 AIP Probe Arrangement

Fig 4.3 Pressure Probe Arrangement at the AIP.

2.3 Distortion Descriptors

2.3.1 Circumferential Distortion

Parameters

1. Intensity^{[4], [5]}:

It describes the magnitude of pressure defect for each ring, i , and is obtained by linear interpolation of the pressures in each instrumentation ring.

$$\left(\frac{\Delta PC}{P}\right)_i = \frac{PAV_i - PAV_{LOW_i}}{PAV_i} \quad (2.1)$$

The maximum intensity of circumferential distortion (for n rings) is given by,

$$\left(\frac{\Delta PC}{P}\right)_{max} = \max \left\{ \frac{1}{2} \cdot \left[\left(\frac{\Delta PC}{P}\right)_i + \left(\frac{\Delta PC}{P}\right)_{i+1} \right] \right\} \quad (2.2)$$

2. Extent^[5]:

It is the angular region in degrees where the pressure is below ring average pressure. It is also measured in the same way. In a ring i with Q low pressure regions, the extent is given by,

$$\theta_i^- = \sum_{k=1}^Q \theta_{ik}^- \quad (2.3)$$

3. Multiple-per-revolution^[5]:

It describes the number of low pressure regions for each ring and is also obtained in the same way. The intensity and extent elements of each low-pressure region are calculated with the help of equations (2.1) and (2.3).

a. Patterns with $\theta_{ik}^+ \leq \theta_{min}^+$

If the pattern has low-pressure regions circumferentially separated by high-pressure regions with extents less than or equal to θ_{min}^+ , it is considered as an equivalent one-per-revolution low-pressure region and the multiple-per-revolution element is one ($MPR_i = 1$). θ_{min}^+ is

generally specified by the descriptor system developer. A value of θ_{min}^+ of approximately 25° is suggested in the absence of other information.

The equivalent extent of the low-pressure region is given by,

$$\theta_i^- = (\theta_2 - \theta_1)_i - (\theta_4 - \theta_3)_i \quad (2.4)$$

The intensity is given by

$$\left(\frac{\Delta PC}{P}\right)_i = \frac{\sum_{k=1}^Q \left(\frac{\Delta PC}{P}\right)_{ik} \cdot \theta_{ik}^-}{\sum_{k=1}^Q \theta_{ik}^-} \quad (2.5)$$

b. Patterns with $\theta_{ik}^+ > \theta_{min}^+$

If the pattern has low-pressure regions circumferentially separated by high-pressure regions with extents greater than θ_{min}^+ , then the multiple-per-revolution element is greater than one.

Intensity is the value of $\left(\frac{\Delta PC}{P}\right)_i$ which corresponds to the maximum value of $\left[\left(\frac{\Delta PC}{P}\right)_i \cdot \theta_{ik}^-\right]$

Extent θ_i^- is the θ_{ik}^- corresponding to the maximum value of $\left[\left(\frac{\Delta PC}{P}\right)_i \cdot \theta_{ik}^-\right]$.

The Multiple Per Revolution factor is given by,

$$MPR_i = \frac{\sum_{k=1}^Q \left[\left(\frac{\Delta PC}{P}\right)_{ik} \theta_{ik}^-\right]}{\max \left[\left(\frac{\Delta PC}{P}\right)_{ik} \times \theta_{ik}^-\right]} \quad (2.5)$$

2.3.2 Radial Distortion Parameters

1. Radial distortion intensity^{[4], [5]}:

$$\left(\frac{\Delta PR}{P}\right)_i = \frac{PFAV - PAV_i}{PFAV} \quad (2.6)$$

The maximum intensity of radial distortion (for all the rings) is given by

$$\left(\frac{\Delta PR}{P}\right)_{max} = \max \left\{ \left(\frac{\Delta PR}{P}\right)_1, \left(\frac{\Delta PR}{P}\right)_n \right\} \quad (2.7)$$

If $\left(\frac{\Delta PR}{P}\right)_1$ is maximum, the radial distortion pattern is predominantly hub radial.

If $\left(\frac{\Delta PR}{P}\right)_n$ is maximum, the radial distortion pattern is predominantly tip radial.

2.4 Compressor Analysis

The following analysis is carried out for both LPC and HPC. The corrected parameters used for this analysis are given in table 2.2. (P1avg is used in the baseline calculation and PFAVG is used in distortion calculation)

Table 2.2 Data obtained from DAMS for Compressor Analysis.

Probe name	Parameter	Location
P1avg / PFAVG	P_{01}	LPC inlet
T1avg	T_{01}	LPC inlet
mLPC	\dot{m}_{LPC}	LPC inlet
CP2avg	P_{02}	LPC outlet
T2avg	T_{02}	LPC outlet
CP2DCavg	P_{03}	HPC inlet
T2DCavg	T_{03}	HPC inlet
mHPC	\dot{m}_{HPC}	HPC inlet
CP3Cavg	P_{04}	HPC outlet
T3avg	T_{04}	HPC outlet

2.4.1 Isentropic Efficiency

1. Isentropic exit temperature (T_{02is}) is calculated by using isentropic equation.

$$\frac{T_{02is}}{T_{01}} = \left(\frac{P_{02}}{P_{01}}\right)^{\frac{\gamma-1}{\gamma}} \quad (2.8)$$

2. Using the above found parameter, the isentropic efficiency can be found using the equation,

$$\eta_{isentropic} = \frac{h_{2s} - h_1}{h_2 - h_1} \times 100 = \frac{T_{2is} - T_1}{T_2 - T_1} \times 100 \quad (2.9)$$

2.4.2 Power required

1. This is given by the equation,

$$Power = \dot{m} \cdot C_p \cdot (T_2 - T_1) \quad (2.10)$$

$$C_p = \frac{\kappa \cdot R}{\kappa - 1} \quad (2.11)$$

2. Percentage of the power required is found for all low spool speeds.

2.5 Surge Margin

1. The performance map of the compressor is obtained as a template from the compressor rig test [6]. The operating pressure ratios and surge pressure ratios along with the corresponding mass flow rates and spool speeds are traced from the template and the performance map is plotted in excel for both HPC and LPC.
2. The surge margin [5] for the baseline test (defined at constant mass flow rate at all operating points) is given by

$$SM = \left(\frac{PR_1 - PR_0}{PR_0}\right) \times 100 \quad (2.12)$$

3. To predict the surge margin during distortion, the following distortion parameters have to be calculated. The inlet strut readings mentioned in the AIP rake arrangement is used as input for calculating the distortion parameters.
 - a. Circumferential distortion intensity of each ring $\left(\frac{\Delta PC}{P}\right)_i$
 - b. Circumferential extent θ_i^-
 - c. MPR
 - d. Radial distortion intensity $\left(\frac{\Delta PR}{P}\right)_i$
 - e. Correlation coefficients (KC, KR, C_h, C_t)

4. A MATLAB program is used to determine the distortion descriptor elements (a to d) using the equations mentioned in section 2.3.
5. The correlation coefficients (a-e) are determined using graphs from experimental data.^[7]

2.6 Loss in Surge Margin Due to Inlet Total Pressure Distortion

This method^[5] has been used to correlate data from a three-stage fan in terms of the above-mentioned distortion descriptor elements with the same accuracy as an existing distortion index that has been verified by distortion screen tests, propulsion system tests, and flight tests. The relation between loss in compressor surge pressure ratio and the distortion descriptor elements is given by,

$$\Delta PRS = \sum_{i=1}^n \left[(KC)_i \cdot \left(\frac{\Delta PC}{P} \right)_i + (KR)_i \cdot \left(\frac{\Delta PR}{P} \right)_i + C_i \right] \times 100 \quad (2.13)$$

Methodology

1. The circumferential sensitivity KC is expanded to include ring-weighting factors α_i , an extent factor $f(\theta_i^-)$, and a multiple-per-revolution factor $f(MPR_i)$.
2. The loss in surge pressure ratio due to circumferential distortion (ΔPRS_c) is proportional to a weighted average of the distortion-descriptor elements over the entire interface plane.

$$\Delta PRS_c = \sum_{i=1}^n \left[\alpha_i \cdot KC \cdot \left(\frac{\Delta PC}{P} \right)_i \cdot \left(\frac{\theta_i^-}{180} \right) \cdot \left(\frac{1}{MPR_i} \right) \right] \times 100 \quad (2.14)$$

3. The loss in surge pressure ratio due to radial distortion (ΔPRS_r) is evaluated for two annular regions. For an interface plane defined by five instrumentation rings, the hub region consists of the inner two instrumentation rings and the

tip region consists of the outer two instrumentation rings.

$$\Delta PRS_h = \left\{ \sum_{i=1}^2 \left[\frac{1}{2} \cdot KR \cdot \left(\frac{\Delta PR}{P} \right)_i \right] + C_h \right\} \times 100 \quad (2.15)$$

$$\Delta PRS_t = \left\{ \sum_{i=n-1}^n \left[\frac{1}{2} \cdot KR \cdot \left(\frac{\Delta PR}{P} \right)_i \right] + C_t \right\} \times 100 \quad (2.16)$$

4. The loss in surge pressure ratio due to radial distortion is the higher of the losses evaluated for the hub (ΔPRS_h) and tip (ΔPRS_t) regions.

$$\Delta PRS_r = \max(\Delta PRS_h, \Delta PRS_t) \quad (2.17)$$

5. The loss in surge pressure ratio due to combined circumferential and radial distortions is obtained by algebraic superposition of circumferential and radial terms.

$$\Delta PRS = \Delta PRS_c + \Delta PRS_r \quad (2.18)$$

6. Correlation coefficients (KC , KR , C_h , C_t) are functions of corrected inlet airflow only, and are independent of the distortion pattern.
7. The relation between loss in surge pressure ratio due to inlet distortion and the loss in surge margin of an undistorted flow due to inlet distortion is given by

$$\Delta SM = \Delta PRS \cdot \left(\frac{PR_1}{PR_0} \right) \times 100 \quad (2.19)$$

8. The net Surge Margin is given by

$$(SM)_{net} = (SM)_{baseline} - \Delta SM \quad (2.20)$$

2.7 Thrust Measurement

The nozzle is assumed to be isentropic (follows the isentropic law mentioned in

equation 2.8) having a converging section. The error in thrust measurement assuming the nozzle to be convergent is insignificant and hence it holds as a good approximation, at least for zero velocity ground testing.

2.8 Turbine Entry Temperature

It is one of the vital performance parameter which governs the performance on an engine. It is determined by many different factors like by-pass ratio, amount of air in the secondary air supply, etc. The data extracted from DAMS with the help the MATLAB code for this analysis are given in table 2.3 The engine is mounted on the test bed. two strain gauge type load cells are used on opposite sides which measures the thrust produced. The sum of the reaction forces measured by the two load cells gives the total thrust produced by the engine.

Table 2.3 Data obtained from DAMS for TET calculation

Probe name	Parameter	Location
mLPC	\dot{m}_{total}	Station 1
CP3Cavg	P_{03}	Station 3
PJDCavg	P_{06}	Station 6
TJCavg	T_{06}	Station 6

1. A MATLAB code is written considering the prevailing ratios of air in every station.
2. Firstly, a finite value of BPR is assumed.
3. Using this value, the core mass flow rate is found given by the equation,

$$\dot{m}_{core} = \left(\frac{\dot{m}_{total}}{BPR + 1} \right) \quad (2.21)$$

4. 4.75% of the core mass flow is used for cooling while the remaining is used in

the combustion chamber which is given by the equation,

$$\dot{m}_3 = \dot{m}_2 - \left(\frac{4.75}{100} \right) \times \dot{m}_2 ; \dot{m}_{core} = \dot{m}_2 \quad (2.22)$$

5. Another 17.71% of core mass flow is used up for further cooling at the exit of the combustion chamber and the remaining enters the HPT as given by the equation,

$$\dot{m}_4 = \dot{m}_2 - \left(\frac{22.46}{100} \right) \times \dot{m}_2 + \dot{w}_f \quad (2.23)$$

6. In the downstream of the combustion chamber 12.18% of the cooling air used will recombine with the prevailing air before entering the HPT given by the equation,

$$\dot{m}_{4d} = \dot{m}_{4d} + \left(\frac{12.18}{100} \right) \times \dot{m}_2 \quad (2.24)$$

7. The mass flow in the downstream of the HPT is equal to the mass flow rate exiting the HPT which confirms that there is no addition of air in the high-pressure turbine. This is given by the equation,

$$\dot{m}_{4d} = \dot{m}_5 \quad (2.25)$$

8. 3.12% of the cooling air gets added to the air entering the NGV in the downstream of the HPT as per the equation,

$$\dot{m}_{4dNGV} = \dot{m}_4 + \left(\frac{3.12}{100} \right) \times \dot{m}_2 \quad (2.26)$$

9. 8.73% of the cooling air gets added to the air entering the LPT as given by the equation,

$$\dot{m}_{5d} = \dot{m}_5 + \left(\frac{8.73}{100} \right) \times \dot{m}_2 \quad (2.27)$$

10. Same as the HPT, no air is added in the LPT as well. Hence the mass flow rate

at the inlet is the same as that of the exit of the LPT.

$$\dot{m}_{5d} = \dot{m}_6 \quad (2.28)$$

11. 1.59% of the cooling air gets added to the air entering the jet-pipe as per the equation,

$$\dot{m}_{6d} = \dot{m}_6 + \left(\frac{1.59}{100}\right) \times \dot{m}_2 \quad (2.29)$$

12. Using the nozzle choking function the turbine entry temperature (T_{04}) is found. The loss inside the combustion chamber is taken as 5%

$$1.16 = \left(\frac{\dot{m}_{4dNGV} \cdot \sqrt{T_{04}}}{P_{04}}\right); P_{04} = 0.95 \times P_{03} \quad (2.30)$$

13. Since the stator of the HPT acts as a nozzle, the enthalpy remains the same. Hence an enthalpy balance between the NGV entry and exit is used to find the temperature at the downstream of the HPT (T_{04d}).

$$\dot{m}_{4d} \cdot T_{04d} = \dot{m}_{4dNGV} \cdot T_{04} + (\dot{m}_{4d} - \dot{m}_{4dNGV}) \cdot T_{03} \quad (2.31)$$

14. An enthalpy balance between the downstream of the LPT and the upstream of the LPT gives the inlet temperature of the low-pressure turbine (T_{05d}). This is given by the equation,

$$\dot{m}_{5d} \cdot T_{05d} = \dot{m}_5 \cdot T_{05} ; (T_{05} = T_{04d}) \quad (2.32)$$

15. Similarly, an enthalpy balance between the LPT and the LPC gives the value of jet pipe entry temperature (T_{06}). The mechanical efficiency (η_m) is taken to be 90%. This is given by the equation.,

$$\dot{m}_{5d} \cdot (T_{06c} - T_{05}) \cdot \eta_m = \dot{m}_{total} \cdot (T_{02} - T_{01}) \quad (2.33)$$

16. The calculated value of the jet pipe temperature (T_{06c}) is compared with the measured value of the jet pipe temperature (T_{06}) and the above process is iterated till both the values are comparable with an error allowance of 5% by changing the BPR.

17. When the condition is satisfied, the program gives the turbine entry temperature as the output which is tabulated and plotted against NLC for both baseline and distorted run.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Performance Analysis

The following performance parameters are corrected to both face average pressure and ambient pressure and plotted against the corrected low spool speed. The parameters (for a distorted test run), when corrected to face average pressure should follow the clean flow trendline under ideal conditions. Under actual conditions, there are other losses which are included in the correction. Hence a comparison between the two is done to analyse the effect of distortion. No such comparison is needed for those parameters where inlet pressure is not involved in the correction.

$$\delta_{amb} = \frac{P_{amb}}{P_{ref}} \quad (3.1)$$

$$\delta_{favg} = \frac{P_{favg}}{P_{ref}} \quad (3.2)$$

The face average pressure is less than the ambient pressure. The face average corrected parameters tend to be higher than the measured local values for a distortion test and hence they follow the clean flow trendline [7].

$$\delta_{amb} > \delta_{favg} \quad (3.3)$$

3.1.1 Total Air Flow Rate

Graph 1:

Face Average Correction:

The reduction in total airflow at maximum spool speed is 7%

Reason: The obstruction due to the distortion screen causes more hindrance during the maximum spool speed when the demand for the air flow rate is the highest.

Ambient Correction:

The reduction in total airflow at maximum spool speed is 13.4%

Reason: It due to the obstruction from distortion screen and the effect of distortion.

Distortion Isolation:

At max spool speed, the total airflow rate reduced by 7.26%. (7.6 kg/s) This reduction is solely due to distortion at the inlet.

3.1.2 Fuel Flow Rate

Graph 2:

Face Average Correction:

The reduction in fuel flow rate at maximum spool speed is 6%

Reason: As a consequence of inlet distortion, there is a reduced pressure prevailing in the combustion chamber (P03). The control system is designed to sense the pressure in the combustion chamber and supply the fuel accordingly. It aims to keep the air to fuel ratio a constant. Since there is a reduced air flow rate there should be a reduction in the fuel flow rate to keep the air to fuel ratio a constant.

Ambient Correction:

The reduction in fuel flow rate at maximum spool speed is 12%

Reason: This loss accounts of the non-distortion effects (as a consequence of distortion, the combustion chamber

pressure reduces) and the effects of distortion.

Distortion Isolation:

At max spool speed, the fuel flow rate reduces by 6.68% (0.15 kg/s). This reduction is solely due to distortion at the inlet.

3.1.3 Thrust

Graph 3:

Face Average Correction:

The reduction in thrust at maximum spool speed is 12.26%

Reasons:

1. Drag produced by the screen
2. Exit Mach number since there is a drop-in exit velocity
3. Inlet air flow rate due to reduction in pressure
4. Combustion due to reduced fuel flow rate

Ambient Correction:

The reduction in thrust at maximum spool speed is 21.847%.

Reason: This loss accounts of the non-distortion effects (Reasons 1 through 4 mentioned above) and the effects of inlet distortion.

Distortion Isolation:

At max spool speed, the thrust available reduces by 6.585% (8.56 kN). This reduction is solely due to distortion at the inlet.

3.1.4 Turbine Entry Temperature

Temperature is a theta parameter. The correction does not involve inlet pressure.

In graph 2, the reduction in TET at maximum spool speed is 10.6% (180K)

Reason: Turbine entry temperature reduces due to a reduced combustion (due to reduced fuel flow rate).

3.1.5 Jet Pipe Pressure

Graph 4:

Face Average Correction:

The reduction in jet-pipe pressure at maximum spool speed is 10%

Reason: Reduced combustion pressure at the combustion chamber.

Ambient Correction:

The reduction in jet-pipe pressure at maximum spool speed is 17.37%

Reason: This loss accounts for the loss in pressure due to reduced combustion chamber pressure and the effects of inlet distortion.

Distortion Isolation:

At max spool speed, the fuel flow rate reduces by 7.1% (34.5 kPa). This reduction is solely due to distortion at the inlet.

3.1.7 Exit Mach number

Mach number is a dimensionless parameter and does not depend on the inlet pressure or temperature. Hence, it is expected that the exit Mach number of both the clean run and distorted run to follow the same trend line.

In graph 4, the reduction in exit Mach number at maximum spool speed is 9.165% (0.11).

Reason: Due to the reduced jet pipe pressure (P06), the pressure difference between the inlet and exit of the nozzle is less and hence it leads to a reduction in exit velocity.

3.1.8 Efficiency

The loss in efficiency of the compressor can be due to the reduced air flow rate at the LPC inlet and due to the probable onset of stall due to non-uniform pressure at the inlet. But in this study, the effect of distortion on efficiency is negligible. This agrees with the fact that a reduction in airflow reduces the load on the compressor

and hence the power required to achieve that particular NL in accordance to the control law of the engine is less. Hence the efficiency is not affected.

3.1.9 Power Required

The reduction in LPC power required at maximum spool speed is 10% (1162.8 kW).

Reason: This is due to reduced load on the compressor as an effect of reduced total airflow at high speeds.

3.2 Distortion Analysis

3.2.1 Circumferential Distortion

Graph 5 gives the variation of total pressure in each of the 5 rings at 100% low spool speed of a distorted run. The distortion parameters ^{[3], [4]} are calculated as mentioned in the literature review and used to find the loss in surge margin.

3.2.2 Radial Distortion

Graph 6 shows that the distortion pattern is hub radial when the spool speed is maximum. This means that the blade region closer to the hub experiences maximum effect of distortion. Refer to section 2.3.

3.2.3 Distortion Pattern

The combination of circumferential and tip radial distortion determines the net effect on the surge margin. A distortion pattern where radial distortion dominates will lead to a gain in surge margin and vice versa.

Graph 7 shows that the distortion pattern at higher spool speeds is predominantly circumferential and hence leads to a loss in surge margin ^[7].

3.3 Stability Analysis

3.3.1 Surge Margin

Graph 8 shows that the surge margin (at constant airflow) of the LPC compressor obtained from compressor rig testing for a clean run is 18%.

3.3.2 Loss in Surge Margin Due to Distortion

The loss in surge margin at higher spool speeds (high airflow rates – corrected to ambient pressure) is given by Graph 9. At 100% corrected airflow (corresponds to 100% spool speed) the reduction in surge margin is predicted to be 2%. This was in agreement with the measurements taken from the ground testing of the engine.

4. CONCLUSIONS

In this study, the performance and stability of a typical twin spool turbo fan engine was analyzed when subjected to steady state, time invariant inlet total pressure distortion generated with the help of a distortion screen. The engine maintained good stability levels even when the inlet flow was distorted and the loss in performance was well within the acceptable limit.

Firstly, a baseline test was carried out without the distortion screen to establish the benchmark performance of the engine. Then the distortion test is done on the same engine (fitted with a distortion screen at the inlet) which yielded the following conclusions.

- 1) The corrected thrust produced by the engine under distorted conditions reduced by 6.585%
- 2) The corrected Turbine Entry Temperature of the engine reduced by 10.6%
- 3) The Surge Margin of the low-pressure compressor reduced by 2%

This study can be extended by using air-jet distortion generators to simulate dynamic distortion patterns to obtain results which provide a more accurate measure of the engine's response during actual flight.

In order to adopt the results of this study, the turbofan engine under consideration must follow the same control law as that of the one mentioned in this study and the distortion screen which produces a similar distortion pattern.

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APPENDIX

Graph 7
Circumferential Intensity Vs Radial Intensity

Graph 8
LPC SURGE MARGIN

ABBREVIATIONS

AIP	Aerodynamic Interface Plane
AoA	Angle of Attack
AoSS	Angle of Side Slip
Avg	Average
cc	Cubic Centimetre
deg_C	Degree Celsius
deg_K	Degree Kelvin
DS	Distortion
DAMS	Data Acquisition and Management System
DECU	Dynamic Engine Control Unit
gpm	Gallons per minute
HPC	High Pressure Compressor
HPT	High Pressure Turbine
Kg	Kilogram
LPC	Low Pressure Compressor

LPT	Low Pressure Turbine
Min	Minimum
Max	Maximum
NGV	Nozzle Guide Vane
psia	Pounds per square inch absolute
PAVG	Ring average pressure
PAVGLOW	Average pressure corresponding to the low-pressure regions in each ring
PFAVG	Face average pressure
PRS	Surge Pressure Ratio
PLA	Pilot Lever Angle
rpm	Rotations per minute
s	Second
SM	Surge Margin

NOTATIONS

English Symbols (in alphabetical order)

a	Velocity of sound
A	Area
Cc	Circumferential distortion offset term
Ch	Hub radial distortion offset term
Ct	Tip radial distortion offset term
C_p	Specific heat capacity defined at constant pressure
h	Enthalpy
IDCC	Inlet distortion coefficient of each ring
IDCL	Inlet distortion coefficient of the distortion screen
KC	Circumferential distortion sensitivity
KR	Radial distortion sensitivity
M	Mach number
MPR	Multiple per revolution factor
\dot{m}	Mass flow rate
n	Total number of rings
NL	Low spool speed
NLc	Corrected low spool speed
NH	High spool speed

NHc	Corrected high spool speed
P	Pressure
P ₀	Total pressure
P _s	Static pressure
P _j	j th pressure probe measurement in each ring.
q	Total number of low pressure regions in each ring
R	Universal gas constant
T	Temperature
T ₀	Total temperature
T _s	Static temperature
T _{is}	Isentropic temperature
v	velocity
V	Volume

Subscripts (in alphabetical order)

i	ring number
j	Pressure probe number
k	Low pressure region number in each ring.
r	Total number of pressure probes in each ring

Greek Symbols (in alphabetical order)

α	Ring weighting factor
γ	Isentropic path coefficient
η	Efficiency
θ	Circumferential distortion extent
θ_i^-	Extent corresponding to low pressure regions
θ_i^+	Extent corresponding to high pressure regions
κ	Polytropic path coefficient

Miscellaneous Symbols (in alphabetical order)

alpha	Angle of Attack
beta	Angle of Side Slip
$\left(\frac{\Delta PC}{P}\right)_i$	Circumferential distortion intensity
$\left(\frac{\Delta PR}{P}\right)_i$	Radial distortion intensity
ΔPRS	Loss in surge pressure ratio

ΔPRS_c	Loss in surge pressure ratio due to circumferential distortion
ΔPRS_h	Loss in surge pressure ratio due to hub radial distortion
ΔPRS_t	Loss in surge pressure ratio due to tip radial distortion
ΔPRS_r	Loss in surge pressure ratio due to radial distortion
ΔSM	Loss in surge margin
$(SM)_{baseline}$	Surge margin at undistorted conditions
$(SM)_{DS}$	Surge margin at distorted conditions
$(SM)_{net}$	Effective surge margin available after distortion